

Literature Review on the Relevance and Role of Digitalization in Generation Z

Osman Bulent EKSI

To cite This Article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 5-12, 2024, p. 150– 179. - 0099-0001-2412-0202.

Our studies are of a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”) “EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform.” (“CURRENT SCIENCE”)

(“Scientific Studies - Current Science “Georgia”) ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

CURRENT SCIENCE

Professor Sabrina
Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewis

""• *Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with*

Review Panel work a monthly multidisciplinary "academic" ("CURRENT SCIENCE ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current

Science Georgia") Science Georgia") Journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""The Journal will be horse the subscribers's address of the first Week Ugh the month."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

- *The Journal continues to be included of all international rankings and*

registrations. Quality articles and Publications Acceleration This ("Scientific Studies

-Current Science Georgia")

""• *Reply or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days.*""

("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Abstract

Generation Z is a demographic cohort including persons born from 1997 to 2012. The most notable characteristic of this generation is their widespread engagement with digital technology. Generation Z was born and nurtured in a technological milieu; hence, they use digital devices and settings in almost every facet of their existence. Digitalization is revolutionizing how humans get information, communicate, and engage in socio-economic exchanges. The word digitalization often denotes the incorporation of digital technology into company operations and societal activities. This integration has resulted in substantial transformations across several domains, including social interactions and educational procedures for Generation Z. The extensive use of the internet and the advancement of mobile technology during this era influence Generation Z's worldview and the tools they engage with. The involvement of Generation Z in the digitization process has substantial impacts on both individual and social levels. This generation is one of the first to directly encounter the effects of the internet. For Generation Z, disseminating knowledge in a digital context, using social media, and accessing online services have become commonplace activities. Rapidly evolving technical tools and platforms are continually reshaping the behaviors of this generation. A significant aspect of digitization is the evolution of communication systems. Conventional communication techniques are being supplanted by interactions on social media, instant messaging software, and other digital platforms. Generation Z is engaged with these channels, creating and disseminating their own material while promoting awareness of societal

CURRENT SCIENCE

concerns. The interaction between Generation Z and digitalization has engendered both technical and cultural-social transformations. This document will thoroughly analyze the dynamics and impacts of this generation within the digitalization process in the subsequent parts.

Keywords : *Generation Z, Digital Age, Generation Gap, New Generation, Impact of Generation Z*

Introduction

Generation Z is a demographic cohort including persons born from 1997 to 2012. This generation has cultivated unique traits and behavioral patterns due to their upbringing in a world where digital technology are intricately woven into all facets of existence. Generation Z is characterized by its capacity to effect substantial changes at both individual and social levels. Generation Z is characterized as digital natives. This generation has been immersed in the internet and mobile devices from a young age, developing social skills within this context. Consequently, they possess considerable proficiency in swiftly accessing, analyzing, and applying information. Generation Z assumes a prominent role in constructing their social identities via the active use of social media platforms. (Duman, 2019)

Secondly, Generation Z is characterized by their capacity for multitasking. This generation have the ability to engage simultaneously across several digital channels. This enhances the capacity to handle information overload, but it may also lead to diminished attention spans. The fast dissemination of information might influence people' cognitive processes and result in a shallow mode of thinking. (Deniz, 2020)

A notable behavioral characteristic of Generation Z is their sensitivity to social concerns. This generation has a heightened sensitivity and proactive stance on topics like climate change, racial injustice, and other social justice matters, aspiring to engage in social movements via digital media. This enhances their social involvement and political participation. Generation Z has a strong impetus for personal and professional advancement. (Yıkılmaz, 2021)

CURRENT SCIENCE

They favor self-directed learning using internet platforms and resources, outside of conventional educational institutions. This has transformed their learning and information access, fostering a willingness to use the knowledge they have gained.

Consequently, Generation Z is characterized by their adeptness in leveraging digitalization, sensitivity to social issues, technical proficiency, and ability to personalize learning experiences. These features significantly influence the nature of their interactions with digitalization and dictate the dynamics of the future.

Aim

Digitalization entails the incorporation of technology into all facets of human, societal, and commercial life. This notion denotes a dynamic transformation that encompasses not only the adoption of technology but also the reconfiguration of current processes and the development of fresh business models. Digitalization is the conversion of social and economic infrastructures by the extensive use of information and communication technology (ICT), data analytics, automation, and digital platforms. (Özcan & Keskin, 2020) The fundamental components of digitalization are data, communication, technology, and human interactions.

The origins of digitalization go back to the early 20th century. The trend, initiated with the creation of calculators and analog technologies, intensified with the advent of the first electronic computers in the 1940s. Initially, computers were used only for scientific computations, but the advent of personal computers (PCs) in the 1970s facilitated the proliferation of digitalization. During the 1980s and 1990s, the emergence of the internet and digital communication technologies enhanced worldwide interconnectedness and established the fundamental characteristics of the digitalization process.

Since the early 2000s, the advent of social media platforms and the pervasive usage of mobile devices have hastened the process of digitalization and its integration into social life. This era also saw the emergence of Generation Z. Generation Z is the first generation to directly see the evolution of the digital realm and to mature within it.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Consequently, digitalization signifies not just a technical shift, but also a transformative process that reconfigures social, cultural, and economic connections. The history of digitalization has influenced individual lives, corporate practices, and societal standards alongside technological advancements. The significance of Generation Z in the digitization process is crucial for comprehending future social dynamics. (Özcan & Keskin, 2020)

Methodology

Generation Z is a demographic cohort including persons born from 1997 to 2012. This generation matured at a time of tremendous digital technological advancement, which has become an integral aspect of digital existence. Generation Z's involvement in the digitalization process facilitates significant alterations at both the individual and social levels.

Generation Z's most apparent involvement in the digitization process is not just as consumers of technology, but also as active producers and influencers. This generation articulates its perspectives, establishes its own networks, and disseminates their views using social media platforms, blogs, and other digital content creation tools. Their epistemic curiosity and diverse methods of information acquisition facilitate knowledge exchange and creative contributions within this generation.

Generation Z is altering conventional social interaction patterns via the use of novel communication methods in the digitalization processes. For instance, in-person conversation is progressively being supplanted by virtual connection. This enables Generation Z to reorganize their social connections and provides the ability to engage in a global community via digital platforms. (TETIK & ACUNER, 2021)

Generation Z's influence on digitalization is also seen in the realm of education. Individuals are acquiring competencies in using technology to enhance their learning experiences and are gaining more autonomy in defining their preferred learning methodologies. Educational institutions are intensifying their endeavors to provide a more adaptable and collaborative learning environment by leveraging the digital habits of Generation Z. This fosters a more democratic atmosphere

CURRENT SCIENCE

regarding access to information, educational possibilities, and professional aspirations. 2023 The involvement of Generation Z in the digitization process has significant implications for both individuals and society. This generation's use of technology, alterations in relationships, and shifts in educational dynamics are essential in shaping new norms and behaviors in the digital era. Generation Z emerges as a significant force influencing the future digital landscape.

Literature Review

A crucial element of the digital era is the communication possibilities provided by technical instruments. Generation Z, including persons born between 1997 and 2012, have direct access to these technologies, which have become integral to their everyday existence. This section will examine the technical instruments used by Generation Z and their impact on digital communication practices. (Tetik & Acuner, 2021)

Generation Z mostly use smartphones, tablets, and computers as their technology instruments. These technologies enable consumers to proficiently utilize instant messaging programs, social networking platforms, and video conferencing software. Smartphones mostly facilitate communication for Generation Z, enabling individuals to engage with many people swiftly and easily.

Generation Z has markedly distinct digital communication behaviors in comparison to other generations. This generation has diminished in-person interactions and increased time spent on digital media. Social media is fundamental to Generation Z's modes of self-expression. Consequently, people have developed practices of expressing their feelings, thoughts, and experiences via blogs, tales, and short films. (Şener et al., 2022)

Nonetheless, these digital communication practices possess some adverse characteristics. The rise in time dedicated to social media may lead Generation Z to experience issues such as diminished face-to-face communication skills, misunderstandings, and communication breakdowns. This condition, which presents several threats to mental health, has become a focal point for physicians and psychologists.

CURRENT SCIENCE

The modalities of contact in the digital realm influence not only social connections but also the processes of learning and education. Generation Z enhances knowledge acquisition via diverse online learning platforms and digital resources, hence augmenting their academic performance via the digital abilities gained in communication. (TETIK & ACUNER, 2021)

Consequently, technology tools are crucial in shaping the digital communication practices of Generation Z, impacting people' social and academic life with both beneficial and detrimental outcomes. In this regard, investigating methods for Generation Z to achieve a healthier and more balanced communication experience in the digital era is a significant concern.

Social Media and Generation Z: Interaction and Education

Social media has emerged as a vital tool for communication and engagement in contemporary society. Generation Z is characterized as a cohort that matured in this milieu and actively utilizes the possibilities presented by social media. The influence of social media on Generation Z significantly impacts educational procedures. This section will examine Generation Z's engagement with social media and its implications for schooling. Generation Z use social media platforms not just for communication but also as integral components of their knowledge acquisition and learning processes. Young individuals engage with their peers via social media, as well as communicate with their educators and academic resources. Social media is crucial in disseminating instructional resources, e-learning content, and interactive educational applications.

A significant benefit of social media in education is its enhancement of the learning experience. Generation Z need rapid access to knowledge and the ability to learn from other viewpoints. In this setting, live broadcasts, webinars, and online discussion platforms on social media enhance the dynamism of learning processes. Moreover, educators engaged in social media might devise answers for the educational demands of Generation Z by disseminating various ways and strategies. (Göçer & Karadağ, 2020)

CURRENT SCIENCE

Social media is fundamental to social interaction and activity. Adolescents acquire knowledge about social concerns, cultivate empathy, and engage in social responsibility initiatives via social media. This contact enables the enhancement of critical thinking skills and the augmentation of collaborative problem-solving abilities.

Nonetheless, excessive engagement with social media may have detrimental consequences for Generation Z. 2023 Issues including social media addiction, test anxiety, and cyberbullying adversely affect the mental health of adolescents. It is crucial for educators and parents to oversee Generation Z's utilization of social media at this juncture.

In summary, social media serves as a crucial instrument for engagement and education for Generation Z. These platforms are used to enhance educational procedures, augment information dissemination, and fortify social relationships. Nonetheless, it is important to preserve equilibrium in this process; adverse impacts, such social media addiction and mental health issues, must also be considered.

Digital Competence and the Future of Generation Z

Digital competence includes an individual's capacity to proficiently use digital technology, obtain information, critically assess, and generate digital material. Generation Z comprises persons born post-1997 and nurtured in a digital environment. This generation is better acquainted with the advancements of digitalization than other generations and has incorporated these technology into their everyday routines.

The digital proficiency of Generation Z extends beyond mere technical abilities. It encompasses digital literacy, cybersecurity awareness, and ethical use competencies. TETIK & ACUNER, 2021 Active engagement of young persons on social media facilitates the enhancement of their knowledge-sharing and critical thinking abilities. Nonetheless, it must be acknowledged that digital competence is significant not just at an individual level but also within a social context. The digital gap may result in disparities in digital proficiency among Generation Z people. The future of Generation Z is intrinsically linked to the advancement of digital proficiency. Educational systems must be revised to meet the requirements of the current generation. The

CURRENT SCIENCE

ongoing development of digital technology is transforming the educational framework and providing more chances for pupils. (TETIK & ACUNER, 2021) This generation may create personalized learning trajectories by embracing novel methods such as online education and hybrid instructional models.

Moreover, enhancing digital proficiency in the corporate sector would influence the job opportunities for Generation Z. The demand from employers for workers with digital abilities amplifies the significance of competences in this domain. Generation Z is anticipated to assume digital leadership roles in the business sector, rendering them a crucial component of the future workforce.

The digital capabilities of Generation Z will influence the future evolution of people and civilizations. In this setting, it is essential to enhance education on digital technology and to broaden awareness and access options. To thrive in the future digital landscape, the digital capabilities of Generation Z must be continuously nurtured and enhanced.

Generation Z and Digital Consumption Behaviors

Generation Z is a demographic cohort including persons born from 1997 to 2012. This generation has matured in an atmosphere where digital technology and internet-based platforms influence every facet of life. This section will explore the digital consuming patterns of Generation Z and the primary variables influencing these behaviors.

Digital consumption encompasses all consumer actions conducted by people using digital tools and platforms. Generation Z's digital consumption patterns diverge from those of preceding generations due to their distinct traits. This generation has matured in an environment characterized by simple access to information, rapid product comparison, and tailored buying experiences. In this context, Generation Z favors online shopping, mostly via mobile devices, and influences their purchasing choices by assessing product suggestions and reviews on social media sites.

A significant component influencing the digital consuming behavior of Generation Z is the notion of social engagement. This generation values companies' responsiveness to social responsibility

CURRENT SCIENCE

initiatives and sustainable practices. Generation Z customers choose decisions that align with both their own wants and societal beliefs. 2023 This generation also values openness and ethical standards in their dealings with companies.

Studies indicate that factors like online reviews, social media content, and influencer endorsements substantially impact the purchase choices of Generation Z. Virtual experiences have fundamentally transformed how this generation engages with companies. Generation Z favors doing research on digital platforms and examining user evaluations prior to using items or services. The internet consumption habits of Generation Z are influenced by technical advancements and societal factors. As this generation emerges as a significant customer in the digital realm, companies must adapt to this transformation. For brand managers and marketing professionals, understanding the digital consumption patterns of Generation Z is essential for formulating future plans.

Mental Health and Digitalization: Challenges Facing Generation Z

Generation Z is a demographic cohort including persons born from 1997 to 2012. This generation has been raised amidst the rapid integration of digital technology and is well-versed in modern communication methods, including social media and online interactions. Nonetheless, this trend of digitization also introduces certain mental health issues.

A significant concern for Generation Z is loneliness and isolation, mostly attributable to social media and digital platforms. Studies indicate a significant association between extensive social media use and elevated symptoms of anxiety and sadness. Generation Z may eschew in-person connections owing to the ever indistinct borders between the digital and physical realms. Moreover, the incessant pressure on Generation Z to be perpetually online is instigating the apprehension of "FOMO" (Fear of Missing Out). It is associated with a phenomena known as Out). This circumstance results in persons often monitoring the lives of others and always comparing themselves, hence elevating anxiety levels. This extends beyond social media interactions and may profoundly impact people' self-perceptions of worth. (BÜYÜKMUMCU & Ceyhan, 2020) A further difficulty posed by digitization is referred to as information overload. Generation Z is

CURRENT SCIENCE

constantly inundated with a stream of both profound and trivial information, resulting in a sense of distraction and fatigue. Such adverse emotions detrimentally impact persons' mental health and exacerbate stress symptoms. (Yıldırım & Kumcağız, 2021)

Moreover, technology offers both advantages and challenges in obtaining mental health care. Telepsychology apps enhance accessibility for Generation Z; nonetheless, they also provoke significant inquiries over the quality and credibility of these services. Despite the establishment of online communities and support groups to alleviate feelings of loneliness, the effectiveness and influence of these platforms remain contentious.

The mental health of Generation Z must be addressed alongside the issues associated with the resources offered by digitalization. Enhancing the quality of people' time in the digital realm, promoting mindful social media engagement, and fortifying online groups that advocate for mental health are essential to tackling the difficulties confronting this generation.

Argument

Generation Z comprises persons born from 1997 to 2012 and is characterized by their extensive usage of digital technology. Digitalization in education directly influences the learning dynamics of people and induces significant transformations in teaching methodologies. The educational dynamics of this generation are mostly rooted in a technology-integrated lifestyle. Generation Z employs a distinct learning approach relative to conventional educational techniques, facilitated by attributes such as immediate access to knowledge, interactive learning resources, and information dissemination via social media platforms. This facilitates a more personalized and adaptable learning approach. (Topaloğlu, 2020)

The influence of digitization in education may enhance student involvement. Digital platforms enable students to engage in autonomous learning irrespective of temporal and spatial constraints. This enables Generation Z to choose courses at their own tempo and based on their own interests. Moreover, techniques like interactive material and game-based learning captivate students' attention and enhance their passion for education.

CURRENT SCIENCE

A significant facet of digitalization in education is collaborative learning. Generation Z favors educational methods that use digital resources to promote collaborative work and social engagement. This fosters the development of social skills and the attainment of diverse viewpoints among pupils. Virtual classrooms and online discussion platforms facilitate the sharing of ideas and collaborative projects among students.

Nonetheless, there are certain obstacles associated with digitization in education. Digital disparity may adversely impact the learning process since some pupils lack access to essential technical resources. Furthermore, distractions and information overload are significant challenges that Generation Z encounters in their learning processes.

The learning dynamics of Generation Z include innovative approaches and technologies influenced by digitalization. Educators must cultivate a more effective and inclusive educational approach by considering these dynamics.

Findings

Generation Z is distinguished as the first generation raised in the digital realm, including persons born from 1997 to 2012. This generation has seen substantial transformations in social, intellectual, and professional domains due to direct engagement with the internet and digital technology. Digitalization influences job development and molds the attitudes and actions of Generation Z in the professional sphere.

Digitalization has fundamentally transformed company operations. Innovative business methodologies demanding adaptability, rapidity, and creativity have supplanted conventional company strategies. Generation Z exhibits remarkable adaptability to changes and emphasizes their digital proficiencies in the corporate realm due to their adeptness in using technology tools efficiently. (Erogluer & Mert, 2020)

The job aspirations and expectations of Generation Z are equally significant at this juncture. These people pursue significance, influence, and sustainability in their professions. When selecting a

CURRENT SCIENCE

career, individuals consider not just financial aspects but also principles such as corporate social responsibility, diversity, and inclusivity. The sensitivities of Generation Z compel firms to reevaluate their business practices.

The professional plans of Generation Z are influenced by remote work, flexible work patterns, entrepreneurial possibilities, and digitization. The advancement of communication technology removes geographical constraints and offers Generation Z access to a worldwide corporate network. Moreover, social media and professional networking platforms influence how these people navigate their jobs.

An further significant feature is Generation Z's inclination for constant learning and improvement. Due to digital instruments, this generation has access to an extensive array of knowledge for educational and professional advancement. This circumstance amplifies the significance of online education platforms and digital resources that supplant conventional learning techniques. The job prospects of Generation Z are influenced by digitization, establishing new standards in the corporate realm. These developments not only modify Generation Z but also alter the whole business landscape and redefine the future. (TETIK & ACUNER, 2021)

Generation Z's Expectations Regarding Digitalization

This section will examine Generation Z's contributions to digitization, their aspirations, and their future outlook. Generation Z is characterized as a cohort born into the digital realm, with a distinct framework of digitalization. This significantly influences their engagement with digital technology and their anticipations.

Generation Z's anticipations about digitization mostly center on accessibility to current information and technology. Swift access to information across all domains, from education to commerce, has become an essential need for these folks. Moreover, Generation Z employs an experiential and interactive learning methodology, placing significant emphasis on the interactive elements of digital materials. (Tetik & Acuner, 2021)

CURRENT SCIENCE

The want to engage with social media and other digital platforms significantly contributes to the identity development of Generation Z. This generation is endeavoring to establish their own brands via the material they disseminate on their platforms and accounts. In this perspective, we may ascertain that digitization serves not just as a technology but also as a medium of expression.

Digital competence is a significant component. Due to their inherent affinity for technology, Generation Z continually enhances and updates their digital competencies. This underscores the need for educational initiatives and policies that foster the development of digital literacy. Anticipated future developments include enhanced personalization, sustainability-driven services, and new solutions. Through digitization, Generation Z is assuming more responsibility in all facets of their life and cultivating an awareness of environmental and social challenges. Consequently, Generation Z's aspirations for digitization include new strategies essential in a swiftly evolving environment. This generation will significantly influence future digital environments by capitalizing on the potential presented by digitalization in education, business, and social sectors. In this perspective, comprehending Generation Z's association with digitalization is crucial in both scholarly and practical domains.

Conclusion

At the conclusion of this research, we have thoroughly analyzed the intricate and multifaceted link between Generation Z and digitalization. Generation Z is distinguished as a cohort that is deeply intertwined with the innovations and transformations introduced by technology, acting as both a creator and consumer of the digital realm. As previously addressed in several parts of the book, Generation Z significantly influences social media interactions, digital communication practices, consumption patterns, and access to information and learning processes. Digitalization presents novel difficulties and possibilities for the mental health and career trajectories of Generation Z. (Büyümumcu & Ceyhan, 2020) Digitalization in education is fundamentally altering the learning modalities of this generation, while the notion of digital competency is becoming more significant. The ramifications of Generation Z's interaction with

CURRENT SCIENCE

technology provide significant dynamics that will influence the future. Consequently, Generation Z's anticipations about digitization may influence both their personal growth and the societal framework as well as the corporate environment. The future will be influenced by this generation's contributions to the evolution of their digital identities and the obstacles they encounter. Consequently, an enhanced comprehension of Generation Z's involvement in the digitalization process will illuminate both scholarly research and practical implementations. In this context, we anticipate that forthcoming studies will enhance Generation Z's engagement with digitalization.

References

- AA Kurt, Busra Little, Meric Boynukara, Ferhan Odabaşı . (2023). Digital Distraction: A Concept Study. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/975168>
- BÜYÜKMUMCU, SB, & Ceyhan, AA (2020). The Social Comparison Tendency of Social Media Users . In *Anadolu Journal Of Educational Sciences International* (Vol . 10, Issue 1, p. 273). <https://doi.org/10.18039/ajesi.682035>
- Deniz, S. (2020). Investigation of Individuals' E-Health Literacy and Cyberchondria Levels. In *Journal of Human and Human* (p. 84). <https://doi.org/10.29224/insanveinsan.674726>
- Duman, K. (2019). USE OF SOCIAL NETWORKS AS NEWS SOURCES: AN ANALYSIS ON TURKISH INTERNET NEWS SITES. In *Gümüşhane University Journal of Communication Faculty Electronic Journal* (Vol . 7, Issue 3, p. 1637). <https://doi.org/10.19145/e-gifder.583735>
- Eroğlu , K., & Mert, İ. S. (2020). An Exploratory Qualitative Research to Determine the Effective Factors in the Emergence of Creative Ideas Based on Innovative Entrepreneurship in Turkey Exploratory Factor Analysis to Identify Effective Factors in the Emergence of Creative Ideas in Turkey). *Of Journal of Business Research - Turk* (Vol . 12, Issue 2, p. 1722). Isarder . <https://doi.org/10.20491/isarder.2020.940>

- Göçer, A., & KARADAĞ, BF (2020). Investigation of the Development of Communicative Skills in Teaching Turkish as a Foreign Language. In Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University Journal of Education Faculty (Vol . 7, Issue 2, p. 71). <https://doi.org/10.21666/muefd.686282>
- Muradiye Ates . (2023). Social Innovation and Good Practice Examples in Turkey in Terms of Social Policy and Social Welfare. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/705050>
- ÖZCAN, M., & KESKİN, B. (2020). Social Transformation in the Context of Digitalization . In Opus international journal of society research (Vol . 16, Issue 29, p. 1). ADAMOR. <https://doi.org/10.26466/opus.775748>
- Sener, H., Arikan, I., & Gulekci , Y. (2022). Evaluation of University Students ' Cyber Security Awareness and Cyberbullying and Cyber Victimization Levels in the COVID-19 Pandemic . Of The Bulletin of Legal Medicine (Vol . 27, Issue 2, p. 142). Association of Forensic Medicine Specialists. <https://doi.org/10.17986/blm.1577>
- TETİK, İ., & ACUNER, HY (2021). A Study on the Feasibility of the Flipped Classroom Model in Teaching Arabic. In Recep tayyip Erdogan University Faculty of Theology Journal/Recep Tayyip Erdogan University Faculty of Theology Journal. <https://doi.org/10.32950/rteuifd.917004>
- Topaloğlu, M. (2020). DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN EDUCATION: EXAMINATION OF MOBILE LEARNING IN TERMS OF MENTAL WELL-BEING LEVEL. In Trakya University Journal of Social Sciences/Trakya University Journal of Social Sciences (Vol . 22, Issue 1, p. 65). <https://doi.org/10.26468/trakyasobed.492918>
- Yıkılmaz, A. (2021). On the word “doubt”. In Turkish Language Research Yearbook- Belleten (Issue 71, p. 149). <https://doi.org/10.32925/tday.2021.57>
- YILDIRIM, O., & KUMCAĞIZ, H. (2021). The Effect of the Epidemic Disease Fighting Psycho-Education Program on the Fear of Covid-19 and Psychological Resilience Levels of Adolescents. In Cumhuriyet International Journal of Education . <https://doi.org/10.30703/cije.858679>

